

WATERSHED DEVELOPMENT IN RAJASTHAN

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ABSTRACT:-Water is an essential natural resource for life. Throughout the history of mankind, the availability of water has determined the location, growth and development of human settlement and the environment. Each influences the other. Watershed development in Rajasthan typically involves strategies to conserve water, manage soil erosion and promote sustainable agriculture in arid and semi-arid region. Techniques like rainwater harvesting, check dams, contour bundling and afforestation are often employed to improve water availability and soil quality in these areas. This help enhances agricultural productivity and livelihoods while mitigating the impact of droughts. Watershed is the basic unit of development for watershed development projects (WDPs). WDPs seek to improve the quality of the natural resource base. Several components and activities are undertaken under WDPs.

In recent past several studies are undertaken to assess the impacts and outcome of watershed development but could not came up with appropriate solution to major challenges. The present study try to focus district wise present status of watershed programmer in arid Rajasthan.

Key words :- Watershed, development, arid region, water harvesting, conservation, water resources.

INTRODUCTION: -

The need of water is obvious for every living organism for its existence. A watershed is an area having common drainage, where the rainwater falling in the area coming within the edge line can be harvested and made to flow out the area through a common drainage point. The main activities under development of watershed are promoting water harvesting and conservation, establishing percolation ponds, open wells, tanks and small reservoirs and improving water quality. The main enterprise or activities promoted by WDPs are to evolve appropriate farming system, encourage a crop-mix of high productivity and high value crops and also to promote social and agro forestry and other income generating activities like dairying and poultry keeping to supplement the farmer income.

WDPs will help reduce soil erosion and arrest surface runoffs. Redirecting water to store excess water run offs in farm pounds, tanks etc. aids ground water recharge and improve the level of wells. WDPs also intend to promote better crop management. Watershed will help in moisture conservation.

The watershed development programme of Rajasthan has made a successful beginning. The initial field results are encouraging. All environmental, social, economic concerns are combined to treat watershed in an integrated manner. In Rajasthan management of water resources becomes most challenging task. The present study aims to bring out district level status of watershed taken up under WDPs and their performance and impacts.

LITERATURE REVIEW :-

Ram Balak (2020) in his research paper "Watershed management in arid Western Rajasthan" elucidates the challenges and approaches of watershed. Where ephemeral drainage system covers just 1/3 area within its 20.87 mha land. In such a vast area, there are total 30398 micro watershed out of which 7771 are sanctioned, 3064 are completed and 4707 are in progress. However, due to physico climate constraints expected result/impacts are not obtained.

Rana Tejbir Sing, Ratnu Bharat and Sukhram (2016) in their research paper "Water Management in Western Rajasthan" highlighted that rapidly changing world where man is blessed with modern technology that has given power to use and abuse the resources. The Western Rajasthan is bestowed with the technology which supply substantial amount of water in water deficient region.

The over-exploration of groundwater by the farmers is contributing to a non-sustainable farming practices. This will not only affect the social life of the people but also the economic life.

Jat Dr. B.C. (2012) in his research paper defined the sustainability of water can be reached only if we seek greater regional self sufficiency, not less. Building our economies on local watershed system is the only way to integrate sound environmental policies with people's productive capacities and to protect our water at the same time.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :-

- (1) To examine various performance indicator that contribute towards effective implementation of the programme.
- (2) To asses overall impact of the programme on

- (i) Ground water level condition, reduction in soil erosion, increase in surface water and other physical condition in watershed management.
- (ii) Land use pattern, cropping pattern and agriculture productivity in the region.
- (iii) Socio Economic and livelihood condition of the communities.

DATE COLLECTION :-

Secondary data have been used to form the research paper. Data was collected from various magazines, newspaper and internet.

Distribution of Sample Watersheds across schemes and districts by size classes.

Scheme	District	No. of Blocks covered	No. of watershed covered	Year of sanction
IWDP	Ajmer	1	5	1999
	Baran	1	5	2001
	Dausa	2	5	2000
	Dholpur	1	5	2000
	Jaipur	1	5	1999
	Rajsamand	2	10	1999
	Sirohi	1	5	2000
	Tonk	1	5	1998
	Udaipur	2	10	1999
	Bundi	1	5	2000
	Total	13	60	
DPAP	Sawai Madhopur	1	5	2000
	Tonk	1	5	2000
	Udaipur	1	5	1999
	Total	3	15	
DDP	Barmer	2	10	1999
	Bikaner	2	5	2000
	Jaisalmer	2	10	1999
	Jalore	2	5	2000
	Rajsamand	1	5	2000
	Total	9	35	
	Overall	25	110	

The detailed list of the district, state (Rajasthan) and schemes studied by various Institutes/Agencies involved in the study is as follows :-

State Rajasthan	No. of Districts Covered	Programme and districts covered	Agencies involved in the study
	14	IWDP : Jaipur, Bundi, Tonk, Skrohi, Ajmer, Dausa, Udaipur	Indira Gandhi Panchayat Raj and Gramin Vikas Sansthan (IGPRS) State Institute of Rural Development, Jaipur, Rajasthan
	08	DPAP : Dungarpur, Banswara, Kota, Udaipur, Sawai Madhopur	
	05	DDP : Barmer, Bikaner, Jaisalmer, Jalore, Rajsamand	

Impact of WDPs :-

1. Increase in ground water level.
2. Increase in surface water and stream flow.
3. Soil erosion reduction.
4. Runoff reduction.
5. Land use pattern, cropping pattern and agricultural productivity.

- (i) Change in land use pattern. Western Rajasthan has shown a very positive change in land use pattern after implementation of watershed management programme, almost all watershed areas have an increase in area under both kharif and rabi crops.
 - (ii) Increase cropping pattern and agricultural productivity.
6. Reduction in workload.
 7. Debt reduction position.
 8. People's participation.
 9. Reduction migration : The aim of this project was also to reduce migration and generate sufficient employment opportunity.
 10. Women empowerment.
 11. Employment generation.
 12. Poverty alleviation.
 13. Improvement in standard of living.

ADVANTAGES FROM THE PROJECTS :-

Impact evolution studies have shown that watershed development projects have fielded significant economic and environmental benefits. This has resulted in enhanced crop yields, income and employment. Other benefits realized are :-

1. Regeneration of degraded lands.
2. Improved moisture availability and an increase in the ground water table.
3. Better returns from alternate crop and land use management systems.
4. Improved fuel and fodder availability.

There are indications also that small formers have shared in the gains of growth following watershed development projects.

WEAKNESS OF THE PROJECTS :-

The major shortcoming of the projects is that these schemes were almost exclusively departmentally driven with people playing a passive role either as beneficiaries or laborers. They had hardly any say in the planning and execution of treatments to be undertaken, were uninformed as to the funds allocated and the costs incurred, made no "own" contributions. The outcome was apathy, lack of a sense of ownership, rampant rent seeking behaviour, resource inefficiency and leakages. And not surprisingly, the expected impact in terms of increased productivity drought mitigation and water resource augmentation did not occur.

CONSTRAINTS, SHORT COMINGS AND SUGGESTIONS :-

As is pointed out, the present study has been carried out using the secondary data available from official sources. There fire a unique compilation of various development activities under different schemes has not been possible. However on the basis of whatever data and information, which were collected for the study, certain suggestions have been made to overcome the constraints met in implementing the project. These are as follows :-

1. A technically sound approach with emphasis on setting and maintaining standards and quality should be formulated by the state government.
2. Simple but robust systems of record keeping, documentation, reporting and funds claims should be adopted.
3. Adding resources to responsibilities where people not only commit themselves to tasks and obligations but are also equipped with the means to discharge them should to be taken care of by the government.
4. Less emphasis was given to people's participation while executing the projects. By actively seeking people's participation long run targets could be achieved.
5. The new Hariyali guidelines have limited the scope of NGOs and independent agencies. But viewing their success stories NGOs must be allowed to widen the scope of their activities but that also under the supervision of Governmental agency.

CONCLUSION:-

Watershed development programme WDP is one of the most popular development programme implemented in the Rajasthan. This programme has been directed towards the promotion of overall economic development and improvement of the socio-economic condition of resource poor sections of people inhabiting the programme areas through natural resource enhancement. The impact of watershed is more focused towards physical; and biological achievement but the focus on social

aspects is limited. There are certain positive trends towards growth of water level, soil regeneration capacity, land use pattern, cropping pattern, livestock production etc.

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